

Reducing Erosion in Cereal fields on hillsides through Agroforestry

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Alignment of timber trees following contour lines on the cereal-growing hillsides of Pierre Pujos farm (source Ver de terre Production).

A farm located in the cereal hills of the Gers department (France) is particularly affected by erosion due to the slope and the history of its fields, which were cultivated in continuous wheat. At the top of the hills, the limestone bedrock surfaces in some places, making cereal cultivation impossible. To counter erosion, the farm has planted lines of trees perpendicular to the slope, following the contour lines. This spatial arrangement helps to stop erosion by promoting the creation of terraces and the infiltration of rainwater. The upper slopes are reserved for grazing to gradually restore fertility, while the more fertile terraces at the bottom of the hills are designated for cereal and legume cultivation. The trees were planted in a lucerne field, allowing the young trees to benefit from a good soil structure and ground cover. The lines of trees are spaced 25 meters apart to accommodate the farm's agricultural machinery, and the trees are spaced 8 meters apart within the rows. This results in a density of 100 trees per hectare, in compliance with CAP requirements as defined in France. (beyond that, the area is considered forest land). The species were chosen for their suitability to the soil and their potential to produce timber in the long term. Maintaining the trees requires two hours of work per hectare per year. Regular upkeep is crucial, as neglect can lead to the formation of knots in the wood. At the farm, having such isolated trees can be problematic, as birds of prey use them as perches in the spring after new shoots emerge, breaking the tops and hindering proper trunk formation.

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